

ISic2921

I.Sicily inscription 2921

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Arancio hypogeum, villa Landolina

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Memo
2. ria [nomi]ne
3. Fortuna
4. ti pistori patri
5. cio[rum]

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1993

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175841

EDR 073826

EDCS 13900573

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio.* Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 584 no.1 fig.23

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